

LINGUA CULTUROLOGY IS AN OBJECT OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Abstract: Linguistic culture is the study of how cultural ideas—such as cultural models, cultural categories, and cultural metaphors—are expressed through the unique features of various languages. This article compares the linguistic cultural domains of various languages using the idea of linguistic relativity and discusses linguistic culturology and the integrated theoretical study of objects as a practical system of cultural values reflected in them. It is examined how linguistics contributes to the structural complexity of the humanities. The analysis of the world as a completely new subject of study of national image, language consciousness, and national-mental traits is the focus of linguistic culture. The reason for this is that linguistics is viewed as something that depends on the group's cultural status in the framework of language culturology. As a result, language culture can be defined as the study of how culture is expressed and reflected in speech and language. This field of research is closely linked to the study of mental and linguistic traits, language consciousness, and national perceptions of the world.

Keywords: cultural, linguistic, language, culture, culturology, semantic, sememes, analysis.

It's common knowledge that the study of lingua culture involves using the unique characteristics of various languages to describe cultural notions, such as cultural models, cultural categories, and cultural metaphors. A set of language abilities is seen as a component of the cultural level in the context of lingua culture. In a number of applied linguistics fields, such as intercultural communication, second language learning, and communicative variations of foreign languages, cultural linguistic techniques are already being used.

It is "a holistic theoretical study of objects as a practical system of cultural values reflected in the language, a comparative analysis of the lingua cultural spheres of different languages (peoples) on the basis of the theory of linguistic relativity." Cultural linguistics is today acknowledged as a philological science that examines

various linguistic unit levels, speech activities, and various methods of providing information about the world of a given language's speakers.²⁰

Cultural linguistics, at the end of the 20th century, emerged as a result of the intersection of culturology and linguistics, drawing a lot of attention from linguists. Lingua culturological schools (such as N.D. Arutyunova, V.V. Vorobyov, V.I. Karasik, V.V.) established a specific conceptual and terminological group in the following century.²¹

As a rule, the emergence of new concepts and terms that correspond to them causes some extreme disagreement within the scientific community. Lingua culturological, as a humanistic science, is one of the rare cases in terms of the definition of its conceptual essence by the scientific community. A comparative analysis of the many definitions of cultural linguistics that are in scientific discourse has shown that nearly all studies have agreed on this idea based on “language-culture”. Language creates culture.

It points out that the object of linguacultural is at the intersection of several fundamental disciplines, such as linguistics and culturology, ethnography, and psycholinguistics.²²

VV Vorobiev emphasizes that cultural linguistics is a multifaceted scientific discipline that examines and integrates the connection and interaction between culture and language in its activities, representing this process as a cohesive element. Therefore, the significance of lingua culturology within the broader framework of the humanities is well-established— it is a scholarly field that has its own specific subject and object of investigation. On one hand, it serves as a marker of the integration of scientific knowledge, which is significant for the contemporary scientific landscape; on the other hand, it necessitates the identification of both common and unique characteristics of the concept being analyzed. The definition of lingua culturology put forth by VV Vorobyov is, in our view, comprehensive and significant because it immediately encourages researchers to utilize a specific approach to linguistic analysis—namely, "system methods." The definition of lingua culturology provided by V. V. Krasnik is grounded in the overarching semantics of "culture - language"; however, it also highlights additional pertinent characteristics of the discipline under examination. Lingua culturology, as a fundamentally new domain of inquiry

²⁰ Маслова Б.А. Лингвокультурология: Учеб. Пособие для студ. высш.учеб. заведений.-М.:Издательский центр “Академия”,2001.-С.35-36.

²¹ Красных В. В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология. — М., 2002. — С.12

²² Верещагин Е. М., Костомаров В. Г. Язык и культура. — М., 2005. — 1038 с

concerning the national representation of the world, linguistic awareness, and national-mental characteristics, represents a field that seeks to both express and define culture through language and speech while examining the national worldview and linguistic consciousness, which is closely tied to the exploration of linguistic traits.

According to W. Humboldt, the linguistic legacy of lingua culturology signifies the development of fresh viewpoints within the humanities research domain. Lingua culturology is naturally fostered by various linguistic and extralinguistic factors.

In this context, it is essential to highlight the well-known topic of "linguistic and cultural studies," which has served as a primary and somewhat consistent methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language for many years. Lingua culturology acts as a "successor to linguistics and regional studies" within linguistic and cultural studies. It is clear that modern scientific approaches focus on a "new system of cultural values" that is both natural and understandable in today's knowledge paradigm, setting it apart from regional studies, linguistics, and cultural linguistics. E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov, the pioneers of the linguistic and cultural orientation, highlighted another conceptual element: engagement in discourse across national cultures: "... a person simultaneously enters a new national culture when learning a language." This is particularly true with regard to the foreign language teaching methodology: "Every lesson of a foreign language is a crossroads of cultures, it is a practice of intercultural communication."

Lingua culturology has a clear interdisciplinary character, combining different knowledge about the humanities. Cultural linguistics as a complex and multifaceted scientific discipline of humanities and culturological nature is interrelated with many related disciplines: culturology, ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, intercultural communication, cognitive linguistics, ethnic psycholinguistics, lingo philosophy and other disciplines.

The interdisciplinary nature of linguistics is seen in the way it integrates other humanistic expertise. Culturology, ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, intercultural communication, cognitive linguistics, ethnic psycholinguistics, lingo philosophy, and many other related fields are interconnected with cultural linguistics, a complex and multidimensional scientific field of the humanities and cultural nature. "Sufficient mutual understanding of the two participants of the communicative movement belonging to different national cultures" is the primary goal of intercultural communication. Because the system of value orientations of its representatives immediately reflects the variations in cultural values, it is a pioneer in

cultural linguistics. The study of linguistic concepts and global classification systems is the main focus of contemporary research.

Without knowing the concepts of national culture, it is impossible to make a full connection. Given the interplay of language and culture, it has allowed researchers to identify what are called “basic concepts” of national culture, behind which are the most important concepts of national consciousness.

Both the term "concept" and cultural concepts have numerous definitions. The concept's linguistic nature as an interdisciplinary education and the intricacy and adaptability of this remarkable phenomenon—which is pertinent to contemporary scientific discourse—determine the ambiguity of interpretations. We believe that such significant aspects of language culturology demand particular attention. It is important to consider how lingua culturology interacts with ethnic psycholinguistics when creating interdisciplinary connections between the two fields. Ethnic psycholinguistics is a new direction that considers speech activity in terms of breaking down national-cultural peculiarities and considering the national-cultural component of speech. Both sciences are closely intertwined, complementing, and enriching each other. If for ethnic psycholinguistics speech activity, linguistic consciousness and communication are the basis, for cultural linguistics it is the definition of culture in language and its reflection in speech.

According to lingua culturology, a group's cultural level is the foundation of its linguistic expertise. Numerous fields of practical linguistics, such as intercultural communication, second language acquisition, and communication variations of foreign languages, already employ linguistic-cultural techniques.

However, other scholars feel that the lingo-cultural research approach, which tries to show a direct link between culture and language patterns, does not satisfy the fundamental requirements of scientific nature. It is "the study of objects as an existing system of cultural values reflected in this language through a holistic theory and description, a comparative analysis of the lingua cultural areas of different languages (peoples) based on the theory of linguistic relativity." For this reason, we can define lingua culturology as a science that studies the manifestation and reflection of the culture in language and speech, which is directly related to the study of the national image of the world, linguistic consciousness, mental and linguistic features. It is suggested to use a lingua-cognitive approach to communication, as it allows to analyze both its general linguistic aspect and its nationally defined component.

Lingua culturological analysis, which has only two objects—the diversity of linguistic units (including syntactic units) and folk culture, the intangible culture of

particular interest to cultural linguistics—displays a complex approach to the study of any linguistic phenomenon in its cultural and linguistic sense. While maintaining the perception of the real world, the subjective perception of objective reality is always vulnerable to sensitization, which is objectified by different linguistic sign subsystems. Everything that falls under the ethnocultural area must be named as culture is a semiotized ethnic awareness. Their texts and vernacular represent cultural knowledge.

However, in the process of searching for lingua culturological mechanisms for describing linguistic units, scholars were faced with the problem of a lack of works that would become the subject of lingua culturological attention. Separate lexical units or groups of words were considered in this context. The result of such research is the formation of a cultural concept with a core that is part of a particular lexical unit. An analysis of linguistic units with distinct cultural characteristics (e.g., “bread”, “homeland”, “samovar”, etc.) leads only to distinct conclusions. Most linguists are in favor of the idea of constructing figurative semantic fields.

Thus, linguistic research that examines the relationship between languages and cultures can be divided into two methodological methods. The name Wilhelm von Humboldt is linked to the first method in linguistics history. According to this Humboldt method, culture is viewed as a singular ethnic and national phenomena, and language is mainly presented as an ethnic or national language.

References:

- [1] Maslova B.A. 2001 Linguoculturology: Textbook. A guide for students. higher education, institutions. -M.: Publishing Center "Academy", . -P.35-36.
- [2] Krasnykh V.V. 2002 Ethnopsycholinguistics and linguoculturology. - M., -- p. 12
- [3] Vereshchagin E. M., Kostomarov V. G. 2005 Language, and culture. - M., – p.1038
- [4] BAUER Laurie, 1993, English Word-formation, “Cambridge textbooks in Linguistics”, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [5] BRINTON Laurel J. & TRAUGOTT Elizabeth C., 2006 (2005), Lexicalization and Language Change, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [6] DINCA Daniela, 2011, « La néologie et ses mécanismes de création lexicale », Typologie des emprunts lexicaux français en roumain. Fondements théoriques, dynamique et catégorisation sémantique, Craiova : Editura Universitaria.

- [7] DURKIN Philip, 2006, “Lexical Borrowing in Present-Day English: A Preliminary investigation based on the Oxford English Dictionary”, in KÖLLIGAN Daniel & SEN Ranjan (eds.), Oxford University working papers in linguistics, philology, & phonetics n° 11, 26-42:
- [8] MORTUEUX Marie-Françoise, 1997, La lexicologie entre langue et discours, ‘Campus, Linguistique’, Éditions SEDES.
- [9] NIKLAS-SALMINEN Aïno, 1997, La lexicologie, ‘Cursus’, Paris : Armand Colin/Masson.
- [10] PAILLARD Michel, 2000, Lexicologie contrastive anglais-français – Formation des mots et construction du sens, Gap, Paris : Ophrys.
- [11] STOCKWELL Robert & MINKOVA Donka, 2008 (2001), English Words: History and Structure, ‘Cambridge textbooks in Linguistics’, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [12] TOURNIER Jean, Précis de lexicologie en anglais, Paris : Ellipses.
- [13] TOURNIER Jean, 1991, Structures lexicales de l’anglais : guide alphabétique, Paris : Nathan Université.
- [14] TOURNIER Jean, 1985, Introduction descriptive à la lexicogénétique de l’anglais contemporain, Paris, Genève: Champion, Slatkine.
- [15] WUNDERLICH Dieter, 2006, Advances in the theory of the lexicon, ‘Interface explorations, 13’, Berlin - New York: Mouton de Gruyter.